

Evaluation of Performance Management components in Micro Scale Enterprise: Its
contribution to their survival beyond the first 3 years of existence

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I hereby declare that the project titled ‘The Evaluation of Performance Management components in Micro Scale Enterprise: Its contribution to their survival beyond the first 3 years of existence.’ is submitted in partial fulfilment for the M.B.A. Degree Human Resource Management with Assam Don Bosco University, Guwahati, India.

It is my research report un aided and the dissertation has not formed the basis for the award of any degree, associateship, fellowship or any other similar titles.

I declare that all sources of information not originally from me have been properly cited and acknowledged.

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This day the 14th of March ,2019.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

MSME	Micro Small and Medium Enterprise
SMEDAN	Small and Medium Enterprise Development of Nigeria
PM	Performance Management
MSE	Micro Scale Enterprise
CBN	Central Bank of Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Microenterprises as a part of Nigeria's informal sector has borne the burden of being unattended nor comprehensively studied or understood (Akerlele 1996). Yet the few studies done on Micro-enterprises explain that that poor managerial structures contribute heavily to the slow growth of Micro enterprises in Nigeria

Performance Management is a managerial structure that is key to ensuring the survival and growth of Micro Scale Enterprises (MSEs). Several studies have been done on the impact of Performance Management on the growth of Small and Medium Scale Enterprise (SMEs), although previous studies have not focused on MSEs exclusively. This research is focused on Micro Scale Enterprise, studying to know impact of existing Performance Management structures on its survival.

Performance Management is key to the survival of any business because it ensure that employees are contributing correctly to set goals and objectives of that business. MSEs are peculiar in nature owing to their size and they face the most threat of survival. There is need to study and analyze for the different components and extent of usage of Performance Management in MSEs as a key to its survival.

This research will be both explorative and descriptive to get findings into the research topic. This will inform the research conclusions and recommendations. Appropriate analysis will be employed based on the type of sampling and data collected.

Primary data will be collected using structured questionnaires and depth interview questions. Secondary data will be collected from journals, research magazines, and articles.

Data respondents will be Employers and supervisors of micro businesses located in Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria. The study will be restricted to MSEs operating in Abuja.

In concluding this project, Inferences will be drawn from available data to show clearly the role of Performance Management to the growth and sustainability of MSEs, This research should also serve as a contributory basis for future quantitative studies on performance management in MSEs.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

Performance management is a means of getting better results from the whole organization by understanding and managing within an agreed framework, performance of planned goals, standards and competence requirements (Armstrong 2004). According to Na-nan, Khahan. (2016) putting in place performance management patterns that are appropriate for SMEs is of great importance and urgency to give these businesses clear directions in setting and following their objectives. This will enable them to continuously develop towards achieving their organizational needs and to sustainably operate under ever-changing environments.

Developing nations in the world thrive significantly on the contributions from its Micro, Small and Medium enterprises (MSMEs) . The role MSMEs play in growing and sustaining a nations Gross Domestic Product(GDP) cuts across employment generation, wealth creation, innovation development, poverty alleviation, Social cohesion and local development (Bidja&Mandiz vidza(2017).

The Central bank of Nigeria (CBN) in a research provides empirical evidence that Peasant agriculture accounts for about 95% of total agricultural output and employment in the sector.(CBN Research Department,2000). It is also estimated that non agricultural MSMEs account for over 25% of total employment and 20% of GDP in Nigeria (SMEDAN,2007).

Notwithstanding the notable contributions of MSMEs to Nigeria's economic growth, several constraints have forcefully affected the optimal performance of MSMEs in Nigeria. Yet industry economic experts have asserted that MMEs have the propensity to play even a bigger role in developing Nigeria's economy and alleviating poverty (Evbuomwan etal,2012).

To enable a good study focus of this research, it is paramount we separate the categorization of Micro, Small and Medium enterprise. According to Nigeria's National Policy on MSMEs, the classification of MSMEs is adopted based on a dual criteria of employment and assets (excluding land and buildings). The classification is as follows;

FIGURE 1: CATEGORIZATION OF ENTERPRISES IN NIGERIA

National Policy on MSMEs(2006)

	SIZE CATEGORY	EMPLOYMENT	ASSETS(Nmillion) Excluding land and buildings
1	Micro enterprises	Less than 10	Less than 5
2	Small enterprises	10-40	5-less than 50
3	Medium enterprises	50-199	50-less than500

For the purpose of this research, emphasis is placed on the employment criteria that qualifies an enterprise to become a microenterprise and this is the basis of the projects primary data source.

A typical microenterprise in Nigeria is characterized by sole proprietorship. The owner is the brain of the enterprise. He or She owns the business idea and most times starts the business alone. Microenterprises are also largely localized in their operations, on the average, based on the business need and the inability of the owner to perform business operations alone and meet customer needs the owner then employs more hands, which could even be unpaid family members.

Various literature reviews show significant studies on MSMEs as a whole but very few studies exist on microenterprises as a singled out sub sector of the MSMEs. This project will be helpful in contributing to the very few studies of microenterprises as a part of Nigeria's informal sector as its findings will contribute salient evidence base for more research and drawing of the governments' full attention

The poor attention microenterprises have received from the government is a major threat to its growth internally and externally. Growth is defined by the amount of growth such as profit, market share, employment, physical output and assets. (Sara Ekberg et al, 2011).Growth among micro firms is not a norm, most startups begin small and die small and never enters a significant growth stage (Davidson, Achtenhagen & Naldi, 2010).

The operative management function covered in this this project is Performance Management. Performance Management is a HRM function that is key to ensuring the growth of

Microenterprises in its daily operations. Some constraints that threaten the survival of small businesses include

- a. In-efficient Management Capacity and structure:** The basic problem of small businesses is the inability of the owner-manager to plan, organize, direct, coordinate and control both material and human resources in the organization to achieve results. (Ebitu Ezeikel, Basil et al, 2016).
- b. Managerial resource barriers:** MSMEs generally lack the understanding and ability to determine the competencies that are required by an employee to fulfil his/her role. These skill gaps exist in all the sectors from micro enterprises to medium scaled businesses(SMEDAN, National Bureau of Statistics 2013)
- c. Longevity:** A major characteristic of micro enterprises is the owner-manager driver of its entire value chain of operations. In the event of death of absence of the owner, the business is forced to collapse. A major reason is that owners always want to retain what is termed as a business secret.

Performance Management is a key management structure for any business. PM is defined as the process of creating a work environment or setting in which people are enabled to perform to the best of their abilities (Abrudan, & Coita, (2008).

The operational business activities of Microenterprises have been characterized by a purely driven owner structure. To this it may seem likely that owners ensure that work is done to meet their profit motive. However the extent to which PM structures exist in micro businesses is not established. This project seeks to identify and appraise the existing Performance Management processes adopted in the daily business operations of micro enterprises. Its level in terms of formality or informality and also to identify areas of needed improvement.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Literature Review: Introduction

In order to provide adequate response to the research questions, it is required that comprehensive literature review is conducted with the aim of uncovering current knowledge and theoretical contributions on the subject. The structure of the literature review is as follows:

2.1. Introduction

2.2 Performance Management

2.3 History of Performance Management

2.4 Performance Management Systems

2.5 Factors Influencing the Determinants of Performance Management

2.5 Performance Management Models

2.6 Origin and Contributions of Microenterprises to the Nigerian Economy

2.7 Study of Micro Enterprises in Nigeria

2.8 Human Resources Practices in Micro enterprises

2.9 Performance Management Skills

2.10 Formalizing The Performance Management Process

2.11 Criticisms of Performance Management

2.2 Performance Management

The phenomenon called performance is age long. Defining it seems much more difficult than measuring it (Armstrong and Baron, 1998). According to Daniels (1989), the word performance is a process, involving a series, of behaviors, directed towards the achievement of some pre-determined goal. The argument by Rogers (1994) and Fitzgerald and Moon (1996), indicates that performance is the outcomes of work. Lebas (1995), defined performance as deploying and

managing the components of the causal model that lead to the timely attainment of stated objectives within constraints specific to the firm and to the situation. According to Zhang (2012) and Otley (1999), an organization that is performing well is one that is successfully attaining its objectives.) Performance is a function of employees' ability, motivation and opportunity to participate (Appelbaum et al., 2003).

Studies indicate that organizations' started to become concerned with the management of individual performance in a holistic way around late 1980s (Marcus, 2008). But the term 'performance management' first came into use in the human resource field in the early 1990s (Armstrong and Baron, 2005). Kandula (2006), and Zhang (2012) agree that human beings possess potential in a few or more functional areas. But for some reasons, utilization and conversion of this potential into deliverable performances is often sub optimal. Performance management acts as a catalyst in converting the potential into performance.

Armstrong (2004) defined performance management as a means of getting better results from the whole organization by understanding and managing within an agreed framework, performance of planned goals, standards and competence requirements. Hendry et al (1997) suggest that performance management is a systematic approach to improving individual and team performance in order to achieve organizational goals. Walters (1995) and Marcus (2008) imply that it entails directing and supporting employees to work as effectively and efficiently as possible in line with the needs of the organization. Fletcher(2001), asserts that performance management is "an approach to creating a shared vision of the purpose and aims of the organization, helping each individual employee understand and recognize their part in contributing to them, and in so doing manage and enhance the performance of both the individual and the organization".

Performance management ensure employees are focusing on their work in manners that aid the achievement of organization's goal. According to Zhang (2012), managing performance consists of three phases: (i) setting expectations for performance, (ii) maintaining a two-way communication between supervisor and employee to assure performance is on track, and (iii) measuring actual performance relative to performance expectations.

Bacal (1999) definition of performance management is academically and industrially comprehensive. He said that performance management is as an ongoing communication process, undertaken in partnership, between an employee and his or her immediate supervisor that involves establishing clear expectations and understanding about: the essential job functions of employee are expected to do; how the employee's job contributes to the goals of the organization; what doing the work well means in concrete terms; how employee and supervisor will work together to sustain, improve, or build on existing employee performance; how performance management will be measured, and identifying barriers to performance and removing them.

2.3 History of Performance Management

It is difficult to say if anyone knows precisely when formal methods of reviewing performance were first introduced. Koontz (1971), suggests that the Wei Dynasty (AD 221-265), Chinese emperors, had an 'Imperial Rater' whose duty was to evaluate the performance of the official family. After many centuries later, Ignatius Loyola (1491-1556) began a system for formal rating of the members of the Society of Jesus. A form of results-oriented performance appraisal emerged in the 1970s, which still exists today. The term performance management was first used in 1970s, but it was not known as a recognized process until the latter half of 1980s (Jain and Gautam, 2014). Over the years, there has been a revolution in performance management (Radnor and McGuire, 2004). Performance management systems are not new, it has been a necessary part of organizational life for as long as there have been organizations (Fumham, 2004). The ancient Egyptians had to 'encourage' their workers to build the great pyramids, they used performance management systems to do so, though unknowingly. However, over time, as our understanding of human nature and the environment in which we exist has changed, the importance of managing performance to align individual goals to a common vision has been recognized as being vital to an organization's success. (Armstrong & Baron 2005).

Marcus (2008) says that today's performance management systems are more refined and are based on the understanding that the dynamic, creative employees that an organization desires and requires cannot be fitted in to a one-size-fits-all model. According to Daft (1999). "The new paradigm recognizes that, as suggested by the science of chaos theory, we live in a complex

world characterized by randomness and uncertainty and that small events often have massive and far-reaching consequences”

Because of the turbulent and volatile, technologically-based, global society, many organizational attributes that were once considered competitive advantages are now easily eroded. Competitive advantages have the traits of being hard to copy, durable, competitively superior, not having an available substitute and not being appropriated (Collis & Montgomery, 1995). Organizations now feel that their people can provide that competitive advantage. The importance of recognizing that successful organizations are those that are able to keep ahead of the competition i.e. that are continuously able to produce sustainable growth of above average returns, now often depends on the ability of the organization to attract and retain high caliber knowledge workers (Rogers 1994). Marcus (2008) agrees that due to the realization that people are the most valuable asset to an organization, the importance of performance management has been pushed to the fore.

2.4 Performance Management System

According to Merlyn (2012), a performance management system is the key factor used in determining whether an organization can manage its human resources and talent effectively. There are various models of performance management. Each model has its importance as a system for managing organizational performance, managing employee performance, and for integrating the management of organizational and employee performance, Zhang (2012). Rudman (2003), believes that performance management system is a means of integrating human resource management activities with the business objectives of the organization.

Performance management system is a kind of completed and integrated cycle for performance management, Zhang (2012). Macky & Johnson (2000) sees the systems as focusing on continuous improvement of organizational performance, and this is achieved through improved individual employee performance.

2.4.1 Purpose of Performance Management System

According to Lawler (2003), motivating performance, helping individuals develop their skills, building a performance culture, determining who should be promoted, eliminating individuals who are poor performers, and helping implement business strategies are the objectives of performance management system. Zhang (2012), highlights that the key purpose of the performance management system is to ensure that:

1. The work performed by employees accomplishes the work of the company;
2. Employees have a clear understanding of the quality and quantity of work expected from them;
3. Employees receive ongoing information about how effectively they are performing relative to expectations;
4. Awards and salary increases based on employee performance are distributed accordingly;
5. Opportunities for employee development are identified; and
6. Employee performance that does not meet expectations is addressed

Armstrong and Baron (2005) agree that the delivery of high performance helps people achieve their full potential to the benefit of themselves and the organization. A good performance management system provides a means for under-performers to improve their performance or make better use of their abilities Marcus (2008). Stuart-Kotze (2006), concludes that performance management systems aim to motivate towards established and clearly communicated expectations, and also, to provide a developmental process for the organization by setting guidelines that assist in establishing future needs and outcomes. In the words of Brewster et al (2003), performance management system typically involves “the setting of performance objectives, the measurement of performance against these objectives, the identification of developmental support and a review process to develop performance and subsequent objectives”. Having a system for managing performance is essential for an organization. The impact of performance management on organizational success proves that performance management system can have a significant impact on financial performance and productivity of an organization, Hewitt Associates (1994). According to Simons (2000) and Holloway et al. (1995), performance management system cannot be effectively designed and

successfully implemented without considering human behavior. Behavior and culture need to be incorporated into the design and implementation in order to get an effective system. Armstrong & Baron (1998) hinged the key reason for having a performance management system in operation in an organization on the finding that people perform best when they know what is expected of them and have helped in setting the expectations. People are better able to perform and realize expectations that are set within their capability levels, and within a supportive organizational structure (CIPD 2005). A performance management system provides a communication channel that can motivate staff and improve their attainment of objectives through the use of reward-based systems. These systems, if implemented in a well-designed and fair manner, can empower and enable people. (IBEC 2007). Also, the implementation of a performance management system reduces employee turnover Flood and Guthrie (2004).

2.4.2 Phases Of Performance Management System

Zhang (2012) in acknowledging the work of Schneier, Beatty and Baird (1987), asserts that a performance management system is classified into three phases:

1. development and planning performance,
2. managing and reviewing performance, and
3. rewarding performance

FIGURE 2: PHASES OF PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT

From above figure, the performance management system consists of three phases: developing and planning performance is the Phase 1 which includes outlining development plans, setting objectives and getting commitment activities; managing and reviewing performance is the Phase 2 which includes assessing against objectives, seeking feedback, coaching and document reviews activities; rewarding performance is the last phase which has personal development, results of performance and link to pay activities (Schneier, Beatty and Baird, 1987).

i. Phase1: Developing and Planning Performance

Zhang (2012) in his work, noted as follows; planning is the first stage in the performance management system process cycle and offers the foundation for an effective process. Planning is a continuous process in performance management and should be executed with great care (Schneier et al., 1987). Planning helps to encourage commitment and understanding by linking

the employees' work with the organization's goals and objectives (Schneier et al., 1987). It usually includes identifying key value drivers of stakeholders, for example, shareholders, customers and employees of the organization. Similarly, according to Armstrong and Baron (2004), objectives or goals describe something to be accomplished by individuals, departments and organizations over a period of time.

They can be expressed as targets to be met, for instance, sales, and tasks to be completed before the deadline. Armstrong and Baron (2004) further state that objectives need to be defined and agreed on. The objectives relate to the overall purpose of the job and define performance areas--all the aspects of the job that contribute to achieving its overall purpose. Targets then are set for each performance area. Rogers and Hunter (1991) stated that goal setting is the fundamental aspect for an organization. They further indicated that productivity gains will correlate with the extent of top management support for and employees' participation in the process of setting objectives.

It is a motivational process which also gives the individual the feeling of being involved and creates a sense of ownership for employees. At the same time, part of the planning phase includes the agreement on a formal development plan for the employees. Actually this plan should be based on requisite skills, behaviors and knowledge and key competencies that will be required to achieve the objectives and targets set. The development plan can also include long-term development initiatives which are usually based on potential and good performance (Nyembezi, 2009). In this planning phase, the supervisors and subordinates are involved in a joint participative process and set organizational goals, as well as specific goals for an individual. Objectives, on the other hand, also create the environment in which an individual will be measured according to his or her own performance and output, with set standards for evaluation (Nyembezi, 2009).

ii. Phase 2: Managing and Reviewing performance

Managing performance is the second element of the performance management system cycle (Zhang, 2012). This step distinguishes performance management as a process from performance appraisal as an activity (Schneier et al., 1987). According to Schneier et al. (1987), every

employee is responsible for managing his or her own work performance. This involves: (1) maintaining a positive approach to work, (2) updating and revising initial objectives, performance standards and job competency areas as conditions change, (3) requesting feedback from a supervisor, (4) providing feedback to supervisor, (5) suggesting career development experiences, and (6) employees and supervisors working together, managing the performance management process. According to the view of Fletcher, in the second stage, enhancing communication within an organization is important for employees to be aware of objectives and contribute to the future development.

Amrstrong and Baron (2004) pointed that at its best, performance management is a tool to ensure that managers manage effectively. Therefore, performance management system should ensure the manager of employees or teams know and understand what is expected of them, and have the skills and ability to deliver on these expectations and be supported by the organization to develop the capacity to meet these expectation are given feedback on their performance; and have the opportunity to discuss and contribute to individual and team aims and objectives. Moreover, according to Armstrong and Baron(2004), performance management system is also about ensuring that managers themselves are aware of the impact of their own behavior on the people they manage, and are encouraged to identify and exhibit positive behaviors.

The actual performance is compared to the desired performance, so the outcome is evaluated and a development plan is set according to the weakness with reference the strategy. This outcome also provides a feedback mechanism to employees. In order to improve the feedback and update and discuss initial objectives, the organization should also focus on communication within employees and between employees and managers. It is important for managers to develop a fully integrated strategy which enables the different forms of communication to contribute to the success of the firm's mission or common goal (Marion, 1998). Moreover, continuous communication or exchanging information between an organization's strategic managers and its internal stakeholders should be designed to promote commitment to the organization and aware of its changing environment and understanding of its evolving aims (Welch & Jackson, 2007). In the second phase, it includes the performance reviews which can be regarded as learning events. Individuals could be encouraged to think about how and in which ways they want to develop. Research by Ashford and Cummings (1983) demonstrates that feedback has strong

positive effects on the performance of both individuals and groups, specifically through role clarification, improved self-efficacy, the establishment of behavior reward contingencies and increased self-regulatory control processes (Ashford & Cummings, 1983). Similarly, according to Armstrong and Baron (2004), the actual performance could also be compared to the desired performance, therefore the outcome is evaluated and a development plan is set based on the weakness. This comparative approach also provides a feedback mechanism to employees.

Figure 3: shows the structure of performance comparing according to the view of Ashford and Cummings

FIGURE 3: ASHFORD AND CUMMINGS PERFORMANCE PROCESS *SOURCE¹*

Zhang (2012) also added that in this phase, coaching and training is an important tool in learning and development. Coaching is developing a person's skills and knowledge so that employees' job performance improves, and helps them to achieve of organizational objectives. Black & Lynch (1996) suggest that the training courses that are offered by organizations must be designed through considering the present and future needs of the employees and facilitate the learning of these skills. A good training or coaching course should improve the quantity and quality of organizations output; increase the chance of organizational success; decrease the organizational

¹ *Source¹: Ashford, S.J. and Cummings, L.L. (1983), Organizational Behavior and Human Performance, Vol. 32, pp. 370-98*

costs and expenses. Moreover, coaching is increasingly being recognized as a significant responsibility of managers, and can play an important role in an employee's working life.

iii. Phase 3: Rewarding Performance

H Aguinis(2013) provides an interesting insight that cannot be overlooked when considering how to reward Performance. By his definition, ‘Performance management systems usually include measures of both behaviors (what an employee does) and results (the outcomes of an employee’s behavior). The definition of performance does not include the results of an employee’s behaviors but only the behaviors themselves. Performance is about behavior or what employees do, not about what employees produce or the outcomes of their work’. He adds that There are also two additional characteristics of the behaviors we label “performance.”¹ First, they are evaluative. This means that such behaviors can be judged as negative, neutral, or positive for individual and organizational effectiveness. In other words, the value of these behaviors can vary based on whether they make a contribution toward the accomplishment of individual, unit, and organizational goals. Second, performance is multidimensional.² This means that there are many different kinds of behaviors that have the capacity to advance (or hinder) organizational goals.

So in rewarding performance, decisions need to be made on what approach to use. Do you use the result or behavioral approach? Employers must be aware of these factors to be make informed Performance Management structures drive their organizational objectives.

According to Schneier, Beatty and Baird (1987), the rewarding performance phase involves three activities: personnel development, linking to pay and identifying the results or performance. In Rahdert's (1960) opinion, the function of personnel development is that the growth of people can be accelerated over and above that which would take place naturally and normally, and then boost the employees' contribution to personal and group goals. According to Zhang (2012), Personnel development has some development principles. First one is personal involvement. All personnel development is basically self-development. Opportunity for development is valuable only if the individual capitalizes on it himself. Organization can and should offer encouragement

and help, but development activities seem to be successful only to the degree that individuals become personally involved in them. Second one mutual objective.

The premise of any development activity in organization, there should be a clear understanding and acceptance of mutual objectives by both the individual and organization. If the objectives are understood and accepted, the efforts expended will be far more likely to succeed. Zhang (2012) also allude that company should offer universal opportunity to every employee instead of single out a few of its people and make opportunities available only to them. In fact, it is difficult to make long-term predictions concerning the ambition, drive, and growth potential of individuals. The forth principle is individual planning.

Development is individual and should be tailored to fit the individual and the situation; attempts to squeeze everyone into the same model may even prove a waste of effort (Zhang, 2012). Moreover, development should be designed to improve performance on the current job firstly, and then prepare the employee for promotion. Employees who get promoted are those who are currently doing outstanding work and thus have been able to demonstrate their capacity to assume greater responsibilities. Next principle is continuity. If a man who abandoned his efforts to keep updating skills or information, he will become antiquated. Especially for nowadays, the new knowledge and skills are constantly being introduced. Rahdert (1960) also points out that the benefit of personnel development. For employees, if the individual skills or knowledge increase, he may create more value and as a result he may receive a sense of satisfaction in the achievement of personal goals and attainment of professional recognition.

On the other hand, for organization, personnel development is able to achieve competitive advantages because of a better qualified and a more highly motivated team, and is able to utilize advanced technology because of the effectively trained employees. Furthermore, training activities should ideally be based on performance gaps that are identified during the performance review phase (Teke, 2002). By linking training to identified performance gaps, training will be focused, specific and relevant. Teke (2002) also points out that relevant training and development interventions and regular performance feedback are important factors in skills retention.

Therefore, the training, development strategy and the performance management system process should be aligned tightly with the overall retention strategy of the organization. Development programmes are reflecting the needs of succession plans and seeking to foster leadership skills. In addition, there is a growing interest in pay-for-performance plans focused on small groups or teams. Small group pay plans provide monetary rewards based on the measured performance of the group or team.

Evaluation and checking feedback are both important activities in this period. In most organizations, they will not have only one corporate scorecard for the company as a whole, but will also have separate scorecards for each division/employee that feeds into the overall scorecard (Huang & Hu, 2007). According to Zhang (2012), the first process is translating the vision which helps managers build a consensus around the organization's vision and strategy. For employee to act on the words in vision and strategy statements, those statements must be expressed as an integrated set of objectives and measures, agreed upon by all senior executives, that describe the long-term drivers of success. From financial perspective, organization should form some kind of profit measure for organization and employee performance. Financial performance measures might include shareholder value such as economic value added, profitability and growth such as sales volume growth and cost reduction, and liquidity and solvency such as inventory turnover and ratio of debt to assets. Then, organizations and employees also need to fulfill customers' commands and needs. The customer perspective measures include client satisfaction, client profitability or time, price and quality (Kaplan & Norton, 1996).

The measures needed in the internal business processes perspective can be summarized in the company's value chain. For instance, the organization could create new products and services to penetrate new markets and customer segments, also to achieve operational excellence through improving internal process and asset utilization (Kaplan & Norton, 2000). The last perspective is learning and growth, managers will define the employee capabilities and skills, technology, and corporate climate needed to support a strategy. According to Kaplan and Norton (1996), organization should pay attention to assess the effectiveness of their research and development process. Then, employee retention, workforce productivity, the number of suggestions made by

employees and the number of suggestions implemented could be treated as the performance measures.

In this phase, pay-for-performance could be used together as a tool to assess the performance. Moreover, in the organization, employees are most likely to perceive that pay differences are made fairly when they are provided with information regarding the appraisal process and employees are allowed to discuss the appraisal results. According to the view of Locke(2004), the pay-for-performance principle involves providing monetary rewards through carefully designed compensation system that base pay on measured performance within the control participants. According to Delery and Doty (1996:802), employee performance appraisal is defined as 'the process of identifying, evaluating and developing the work performance of the employee in the organization, so that organizational goals and objectives are effectively achieved while, at the same time, benefiting employees in terms of recognition, receiving feedback, and offering career guidance'.

Appraisals can be based on results or behavior. Behavior-based appraisals focus on the behaviors of individuals necessary to perform the job effectively, whereas results-oriented appraisals focus merely on the consequences of those behaviors (Delery & Doty, 1996).Therefore, procedural justice concerns are central to ensuring that employees perceive the process of performance appraisals, and the linkage of appraisal to pay, to be fair (Greenberg,1996). In most situations, properly designed pay-for-performance systems will lead to better performance results. Pay-for-performance systems make major contributions to performance through two main mechanisms. First, they positively influence the motivation to perform. Second, they impact the attraction and retention patterns of organizations, thereby affecting the ability of individuals available to perform. Pay-for-performance systems can deliver monetary rewards at the individual, small group, and/or divisional or organizational level. All of this impact of different levels can positively impact performance.

Similarly, Merlyn (2012), sees performance management is an ongoing process with several components. These components are closely related to each other and the poor implementation of any of them has a negative impact on the performance management system as a whole. She expanded the relationship among the components as shown in the diagram below:

Source: Merlyn (2012), “Performance Management Systems – Its Challenges”

FIGURE 4: COMPONENTS OF PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT BY MERLYN

a. Prerequisites:

There are two important prerequisites that are required before a performance management system is implemented: (i) knowledge of the organization’s mission and strategic goals and (ii) knowledge of the job in question. These two pre requisites was postulated by Aguinus (2013) .This also supported by a recent studies in 2018 that asserts that , In order for an organization to manage the performance of their employees, they will first need to identify the performance level needed to manage the overall organization. This will primarily involve a mission statement to highlight the performance that is required and the all-inclusive goals of the organization. (Torrington, Hall and Taylor, 2008)

Once the goals for the entire organization have been established, similar goals cascade downward, with functional business units setting objectives to support the organization's overall mission and objectives. The cascading continues downward until each employee has a set of goals compatible with those of the organization. To have an effective start in developing a formal PM structure, this pre-requisite should be same for all organizations from Micro scale to large co-corporations.

Herman Aguinis (2013) further emphasizes that if the relationship between the organization's mission and strategies and the unit's mission and strategies is not clear, there will be a lack of clarity regarding what each employee needs to do and achieve to help the organization get there. An online study center shows the Performance Management sequence of an effective PM process. An additional sequence is added to the structure to accommodate the PM prerequisites sighted by Herman Aguinis (2013).

b. Performance Planning:

The performance planning discussion includes a consideration of both results and behaviours, as well as a developmental plan. At a minimum, the plan should include identifying areas that need improvement and setting goals to be achieved in each area. This performance planning discussion includes a consideration of both results and behaviors as well as a development plan. Performance planning includes the consideration of results and behaviors and the development plan. Once the prerequisites are met and the planning phase has been completed, we are ready to begin the implementation of the performance management system. This includes performance execution, assessment, review, and renewal

c. Performance Execution:

At the performance execution stage, the following factors must be present; commitment to goal achievement, ongoing performance feedback and coaching, communication with supervisor, collecting and sharing performance data and preparing for performance interviews. Also supervisors have primary responsibility over the following issues of; observation and documentation, updates, feedback, resources and reinforcement.

d. Performance Assessment:

In the assessment phase, both the employee and manager are responsible for evaluating the extent to which the desired behaviors have been displayed, and whether the desired results have been achieved. In the assessment phase, both the employee and the manager are responsible for evaluating the extent to which the desired behaviors have been displayed, and whether the desired results have been achieved. The assessment or appraisal is an opportunity to take an overall view of work content, loads and volume. A typical appraisal review will: look back at what was done, how it was done and look forward if any learning and development needs can be identified.

It is important that both the employee and the manager take ownership of the assessment process. The manager fills out her appraisal form, and the employee should also fill out his form. The fact that both parties are involved in the assessment provides good information to be used in the review phase.

e. Performance Review:

The performance review stage involves the meeting between the employee and the manager to review their assessments. This meeting is usually called the appraisal meeting or discussion. This involves the meeting between the employee and the manager to review their assessments. This meeting is usually called the appraisal meeting or discussion. The appraisal meeting is important because it provides a formal setting in which the employee receives feedback on his or her performance

f. Performance Renewal and re-contracting:

This final stage is identical to the performance planning component. The main difference is that the renewal and re-contracting stage uses the insights and information gained from the other phases

Brewster et al (2003) states that a performance management system typically involves “the setting of performance objectives, the measurement of performance against these objectives, the identification of developmental support and a review process to develop performance and subsequent objectives”. The performance management system is a way of providing a

measurement of the performance of the organization, the team and the individual through a variety of performance measurement techniques (Price, 2000).

Essentially, this is identical to the performance planning component. The main difference is that the renewal and re-contracting stage uses the insights and information gained from the other phase. In this stage also, fresh set of goals are established for an employee and new deadline is provided for accomplishing those objectives.

The employee is clearly communicated about the areas in which the employee is expected to improve and a stipulated deadline is also assigned within which the employee must show this improvement. This plan is jointly developed by the employee and the employer and appraisal and is mutually approved.

2.5 Factors Influencing the Determinants of Performance

The factors that determine performance are affected by the employee (i.e., abilities and previous experience), human resources (HR) practices, and the work environment. For example, some companies offer more opportunities for training than do others. At the top of the list in terms of annual training investment are IBM (\$1 billion), Accenture (\$717 million), and Ford Motor (\$500 million).⁵ In these companies, declarative knowledge is not likely to be a big problem because, when lack of knowledge is identified, employees have multiple opportunities to fill in the gap. However, performance problems may be related more to procedural knowledge and motivation. In terms of procedural knowledge, employees may actually have the knowledge to perform certain tasks but may not have the skill to do them because of lack of opportunity for practice. In terms of motivation, downsizing interventions may have caused a “survivor syndrome,” which includes retained employees’ feelings of frustration, resentment, and even anger. These feelings are likely to have strong negative effects on motivation, and employees may expend minimal energy on their jobs. Thus, there are three individual characteristics that determine performance: procedural knowledge, declarative knowledge, and motivation. In addition, HR practices and the work environment can affect performance. When addressing

performance problems, managers first need to identify which of these factors is hampering performance and then help the employee improve his or her performance.(Aguinuis 2013)

2.6 Performance Management Models

A number of frameworks have been presented over the years that are aimed at assisting organizations to develop and implement performance management systems within their organizations (Marcus, 2008). In the following section, selected relevant frameworks are considered, each representing different ways of perceiving a performance management system.

2.6.1 Performance Appraisal Model

Gunnigle and Flood (1990) describe performance appraisal as:“A systematic approach to evaluating employee performance, characteristics and/or potential, with a view to assisting decisions in a wide range of area such as pay, promotion, employee development and motivation”. Groate (1996) states that performance appraisal is such a commonplace in organizational life, that every company has an appraisal system. Weightman (2001) describes it as a well established way of providing milestones, feedback, guidance and monitoring of staff. Lawler (2003) notes that virtually every organization has a performance management system that is expected to accomplish a number of important objectives with respect to human capital management. Lawler goes on to state that although this system can make a positive contribution to a company, it is less clear what makes performance management systems effective. Providing feedback to employees on their performance is a central element of effective approaches to performance management.

Outlining the purpose of performance appraisal, Gunnigle and Flood (1990) suggest that the performance management loop provides the framework within which systematic appraisal can take place.

Source: Gunnigle and Flood (1990)

FIGURE 5: PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT LOOP

The establishment of a formal appraisal system is a prerequisite to effective performance management as it provides a dedicated period of time for managers and supervisors to meet with their staff and discuss a range of factors relating to work performance (Gunnigle, et al, 2002).

2.6.2 Management by Objective Model

Setting of performance objectives is one of the most important aspects of performance appraisal process is the participation in the (Korsgaard & Roberson, 1995). Gunnigle, et al. (2002) alludes that setting of objectives is the foundation of the performance management process and for it to be effective objectives need to be achievable and agreed between managers and their employees. Management by objectives (MBO) is a management model that aims to improve the performance of an organization by clearly defining objectives that are agreed to by both management and employees (Drucker, 1954).

Objectives at departmental level have a close alignment to organisational goals and specifically define targets. Individual objectives are related specifically to the role of the individual and the contribution that they are expected to make to the achievement of unit goals. Colbridge & Pilbeam (1998) believe that the manager should set the objectives, which would be agreed upon by the employee. They devised that objectives need to be SMART, i.e. Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Timely.

Heathfield (2000) believes that managers are in no position to set work objectives and the blunt truth is that, if employees have any work objective at all, most people set their own. She goes further to say, that today in an era of knowledge work and the knowledge worker, so-called 'bosses' are in no position to set work objectives for employees, monitor their accomplishments or supervise their pursuits. According to Siobhan (2005), for effective objective setting, that are realistic to the employee and ultimately aim to achieve the overall strategic goals of the organization; management and employees must communicate and work together to set attainable and meaningful objectives.

It is important that managers know the job of the employee and the skills, knowledge and attitudes needed to do the job. It is only with this understanding that both parties can achieve the overall aim of setting individual and team objectives (Siobhan, 2005)

Armstrong & Baron (2005) state that managing by objectives has a philosophy that involves clarifying with managers the key results and performance standards that must be achieved and use the performance reviews to measure and discuss progress towards results by referencing to

the objectives. This theory was put forward initially by Drucker (1961), and is a “technique aimed at tying performance ratings to unambiguous, measurable and relevant personal objectives” (Price, 2000). What occurs in these types of systems is that realistic goals are set, plans are laid out to show how the goals will be achieved, and with employees participating actively in both the goal-setting and action-planning stages. There is then a regular review of individual progress towards the goal (Marcus, 2008)

2.6.3 360 Degree Feedback Model

Ward (1997) define 360 degree feedback as ‘the systematic collection and feedback of performance data on an individual or group derived from a number of stakeholders’. McCarthy and Pearson (2001) define it as the practice of collecting perceptions of an employee’s performance from sources such as subordinates, customers and superiors.

According to Kirksey (2000), the aim of the 360-degree feedback is to achieve a broader view of employee performance by pooling feedback from both internal and external customers to receive a broader, more accurate perspective on employees. Fletcher (1998) goes further to say that 360-degree, certainly in theory should lead to a more objective picture of an employee’s contribution, strengths and development needs.

Fletcher believe that 360-degree feedback has the ability to corral a range of customer feedback, as each group offers a new, unique view and produces a much more complete picture of an employee’s performance. Shipper et al (2007) imply that the use of the 360-degree feedback model is effective as a management or pedagogical development intervention. Feedback must be given within the context of a broader objective, that is, to reveal areas where further skill improvements are needed and provide a mechanism and support structure to effect the changes.

2.6.4 Balanced Scorecard Model

Balanced scorecard model is a multidimensional approach to performance management planning, control and decision-making process that is linked specifically to organizational

strategy (Marcus, 2008). The technique was developed by Kaplan and Norton at the Harvard Business School since the early 1990's.

Sharif (2002) alludes that the scorecard entails defining a number of perspectives to be measured to provide a means for both forecasting and historic analysis, these perspectives are based on the realization of key factors which embody the organization's business strategy. Sharif outlines the typical perspectives of Kaplan and Norton generally cited usually are: The Learning and Growth Perspective; The Business Process Perspective; The Customer Perspective; The Financial Perspective

According to Kaplan and Norton, (1992, 1996), the Balanced Scorecard is potentially a powerful tool by which senior managers can be encouraged to address the fundamental issue of effectively deploying an organization's strategic intent? Balanced Scorecard model suggests that organisations choose a small number of key indicators relative to each perspective and which reflect the goals contained in the corporate vision. Objectives should be achieved for each perspective within a specified time. The scorecard is designed to enable organizations focus on critical objectives and align the performance of the individual with the overall business strategy (Siobhan, 2005).

According to Professor Kaplan, 'The Balanced Scorecard' provides the required language, it is the missing link which fills the gap between the vision and strategy of an organization, developed at the top and the things people down in the organization, at the frontline are doing. This is done by linking vision and strategy to employee's everyday actions by translating the abstract strategy into clear initiatives and strategies and relating these to clear tangible strategic outcomes. Krause (2003) suggests that strategic approaches like the balanced scorecard are financially driven and therefore aspects such as motivation are difficult to address.

FIGURE 6: PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT SCORECARD

Source: Kaplan & Norton, (1996)

According to Klot and Martin (1998), performance management system require the four dimensions of the balanced scorecard i.e. financial, community/customer, internal business processes; and growth/innovation and learning. The balanced scorecard is designed to be at the center of an organization’s performance management planning and control mechanisms to effectively deploy strategy, to link operational practices with strategic intent, and facilitate objective performance measurement (Marcus, 2008).

The Literature review also looks into Microenterprises as major player in the informal sector from a global and indigenous context. With more emphasis drawn to the Nigerian economy as

required from the research topic. It further draws down to Performance management as a key Human Resource Management practice that can contribute to increasing the survival of Microenterprises beyond its first 3 years.

2.7 Origin and Contributions of Microenterprises to the Nigerian Economy

The economic downturn that followed the collapse of the world oil market in 1980s and the financial crisis in Asia in the 1990s brought to fore the important role of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). Prior to this, attempts of developed and developing countries to eradicate poverty focused on the development of large scale industries, based on the traditional economy of scale theory.(Grace et al 2013).

Since the MSME sector was brought to a noticeable front, Nations around the world have benefitted immensely from the seemingly hidden fortunes of their MSMEs. , Nations around the world have benefitted immensely. Aganga (2013) in a published paper provides aggregate data on the contribution of SMEs and informal enterprises in various categories of countries to GDP and total employment: He states that SMEs in high income countries contribute 55% to GDP and over 65% of total employment. In middle income countries they account for over 70% of GDP and over 95% of total employment and 60% of GDP and over 70% of total employment in low income countries.

Added to the contributions to a nations GDP and employment, Micro and small scale enterprises (MSEs) have been widely acknowledged as the springboard for sustainable economic development. They contributes to the increase in per capital income and output and also boosts the development of indigenous entrepreneurship, enhance regional economic balance through industrial dispersal and generally promote effective resource utilization that are considered to be critical in the area of engineering economic development (Tolentino, 1996; Oboh, 2004; Odeh, 2005).

Nigeria is a developing economy with vast economic structure of which ME are a major component comprising a significant proportion of the country's informal structure. Several economic based research show that MSMEs contribute to growing and sustaining Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product(GDP) which cuts across employment generation, wealth creation, innovation development, poverty alleviation, Social cohesion and local development (Bidja & Mandiz vidza(2017).

A formal account of MSME's in Nigeria from the foremost financial regulatory institution of Nigeria, the Central bank of Nigeria (CBN) provides empirical evidence that Peasant agriculture accounts for about 95% of total agricultural output and employment in the sector. (CBN Research Department, 2000). It is also estimated that nonagricultural MSMEs account for over 25% of total employment and 20% of GDP in Nigeria (SMEDAN, 2007).

2.8 Micro Enterprises in Nigeria

In Nigeria, various literature reviews show significant studies on MSMEs as a whole but very few studies exist on microenterprises as a singled out sub sector of the MSMEs. Economic activity that falls outside the purview of government accounting is known by various names as informal, hidden, underground, black, gray, clandestine, illegal, shadow, and parallel (Thomas, 1992; Feige, 1990; Schneider and Enste, 2000).

This lays the basis of microenterprises as a part of Nigeria's informal sector and has such borne the burden of being unattended. This poor grounds gained by this gray sector is further purported by , Ajakaiye and Akerele (1996) stating that Nigeria's informal economy still remains an enigma as it has neither been comprehensively studied nor understood. Further Literature reveal that;

'One of the major constraints to development policymaking and economic management in Nigeria is the paucity of credible statistics and systematic evidence on the informal sector. Despite the wide range of informal sector economic processes and activities, current knowledge of the size, causes, characteristics, and dynamics of the informal sector remains very scanty and inadequate (Oduh et al, 2008)'.

3 This project lends its contributions to the few research carried out on the Nigerian informal sector.

2.8.1 Conceptual framework of Micro Enterprises.

There is no conclusive definition of the informal sector from a global perspective, although the term has been in existence since the 1970s “Informal” usually refers to unregistered, unregulated, and untaxed businesses, including service enterprises, production activities, and street vendor sales (*Anita Spring 2009*).

This description of an informal sector where Micro enterprises belong have some school of thought that argue against the enterprise owners in the sector. In these arguments, The legalist school sees the informal economy as comprised of plucky entrepreneurs who choose to operate informally in order to avoid the unnecessary and burdensome costs, time and effort of formal registration and who need legal rights to convert their assets into formal property (de Soto 1989, 2000). The voluntarist school also argues in favor of the legalist school in that it sees the informal economy as comprised of entrepreneurs who choose to operate informally in order to avoid taxation, commercial regulations, electricity and rental fees, and other costs of operating formally (e.g. Maloney 2004).

Hart (2001) strongly supports these schools of thought by describing the informal sector as self organized energies of people escaping government strictures. Despite the arguments, the informal economy has continued to grow and has appeared in new forms. Today, it represents a significant share of the global economy and workforce.

In Nigeria Micro enterprises as key players in this sector are characterized by sole proprietor businesses, and in some instances, joint-partnership businesses which can be found both in rural and urban settlements across the country. However, the nature of the economic activities engaged in varies considerably from one locality to another. For example, in the rural areas, farming activities and allied occupations such as hunting, fishing, weaving, blacksmithing, basket and pot making as well as leather works are more prevalent. In urban centers like Lagos, Enugu, Abuja, Port Harcourt, and Kano, informal economic activities include trading, small scale manufacturing and repairing industries, such as carpentry, upholstery, furniture making,

woodworks, metal works, bakery, gold smiting, tailoring, bricklaying, and printing. Those in the repairing occupations include, among others, the automobile mechanics, electricians, clock and watch repairers, and cobblers, (Olowu & Okotoni, 1996)

2.8.2 Definition of Micro Enterprises

Micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) are companies whose headcount or turnover falls below certain limits. The definitions change over time and depend, to a large extent, on a country's level of development. Thus, what is considered small in a developed country like the USA could actually be classified as large in a developing country like Nigeria (Evbuomwan et al 2013)?

A very broad classification is provided by (Stanely and Morses 1965), where they classified enterprises into eight by size. They adopted the functional approach, and emphasized how small and medium sized industries differ from larger industries by bringing out clearly the differing characteristics which include little specialization, close personal contact of management with production workers and lack of access to capital. They argued that establishments employing not less than 100 workers should be defined as medium sized whereas those with less than 100 employees be defined as small sized.

Going by this definition its Microenterprises run the risk of fading away into the too broad categorization by Stanely and Morses 1965. However as it concerns Nigeria, a more precise definition is provided by the National Council on Industry of Nigeria (1996) which at its 9th Meeting adopted the report of its Sub Committee on Classification of Industrial Enterprises in Nigeria and approved a new set of classifications and definitions of the cottage/micro and small scale enterprises. According to the Council, cottage/micro industry is an industry whose total cost, including working capital but excluding cost of land, is not more than N1 million and a labour size of not more than 10 workers; while small scale enterprises is an industry whose total cost, including working capital but excluding cost of land, is over N1 million but not more than N40 million and a labour size of between 11 and 35 workers.

The definition, is supported by the International Finance Corporation (IFC, World Bank 2010) that categorizes MSMEs based on its share in total employment, stating that a micro enterprise employs 1–9 employees; small enterprise employs: 10–49 employees; and medium enterprises: 50–249 employee.

2.8.3 Challenges of Micro Enterprises

According to *Tendai, Mandipaka (2015)* challenges faced by Micro enterprises in developing countries have been learned to be the same to those of their counterparts in developed countries. The only difference between the challenges that confront micro enterprises in developing and developed countries is the fact that the magnitude of their differences weighs more negatively for developing countries. For example in South Africa where they conducted the research, in their conclusion, it is stated that it remains regrettable that despite the role played by the SMMEs sector and the support that they get in South Africa, more than 70 percent of these ventures still fail within three years after being established (Biyase, 2009; Fatoki & Smit, 2011).

In Nigeria, Micro enterprises by their definition have been placed at the lowest strata of industries and this has affected their growth and contribution to Nigeria's economy greatly. Besides the continuous neglect by the government as asserted by Ajakaiye and Akerele 1996, studies also reveal that whereas micro/cottage, small and medium scale enterprises serve as the engine of economic development of any developing nation, statistics show that 3 out of 4 of these small businesses die every year in Nigeria (Nzelibe, 1996). However, despite donor agency and Non-governmental support to the sector of enterprises for over 30 years, the expected growth and transition of most informal-sector micro- to small-scale enterprises into medium- or large-scale enterprises have not occurred (Anita Spring 2009)

What is responsible for the high mortality of Microenterprises in Nigeria, especially before the growth stage of their business life cycle? Various literature seeks to provide answers to this question. Baumbach (1983) contend that most of problems of small scale enterprises are external to it. According to him "among the more important of these external or environmental factors are those related to capital shortage, taxation and regulations etc. While Baumbach focuses of

financial constraints another study emphasizes on other non-financial constraint, this study argues that The two prerequisites for entrepreneurial success are human and financial capital but loans matter only when skills and savings are present, more so according to Bates (1997), ‘no serious studies have demonstrated that small amounts of debt can overcome human capital deficiencies that otherwise minimize chances for business success. This studies place importance on the Human capital element of micro enterprises and the effect of its lack in the survival of an enterprise.

To support the non-financial constraint faced by Micro enterprises, a study by Tendai and Mandipaka 2015, reveals that the growth and survival of SMMEs are threatened by impediments that may exist in the operations and management functional areas of the business. A number of studies have also identified factors, such as inexperience in the field of business, lack of technical knowledge, poor managerial skills, lack of planning skills, and lack of market research skills, as the main challenges hindering the success of SMMEs in developing countries (Baron & Shane, 2007; Olutunla & Obamuyi, 2008; Schwartz & Hornych, 2010). Even entrepreneurs with technical backgrounds may find challenges in managing operations and management functional areas of the business (Omerzel & Antonic, 2008; Mbonyane & Ladzani, 2010).

The numerous studies that focus on the challenges faced by SMEs is just enough to trigger lasting solutions or interventions both from the government and from business owners who should build their competencies in business management. More studies exposing some of the challenges indicate that SMEs competitiveness in developing countries is hindered because of a lack of human resource and development skills and access to adequate finance (Urban and Naidoo 2012). Osoimehin, K. Jegede et al (2012) submit that despite government institutional and policies support to enhancing the capacity of small and medium scale enterprises, small and medium scale enterprises has fallen short of expectations.

SMEs are faced with significant challenges that compromise their ability to function and to contribute optimally to the economy. Micro and small scale enterprises (MSEs) in Nigeria have not performed creditably well and they have not played expected significant role in economic growth. They equally has not influenced apprentice training so as to accelerate employment and

poverty alleviation in order to foster Nigerian economic development. This situation has been of great concern to the government, citizen, operators, practitioners and organized private sectors. With the realization of the potentials of the MSEs, governments at different level in Nigeria have put up a lot of support programmes to promote and sustain their development.

A different perspective from a study by Igbekele, Adebisi (2004) blames the poor performance and efficiency of Micro enterprises in Nigeria to the level of education and age of enterprise owners, at the time of inception of such enterprises.

Elijah U, Nsikak J (2011) give reasons why Micro enterprises have not performed optimally at least to the extent of the government and non- government support the sector has received and most of the reasons are in concurrence with the studies already provided. The reasons are as follows;

- a. In-efficient Management Capacity and structure:** The basic problem of small businesses is the inability of the owner-manager to plan, organize, direct, coordinate and control both material and human resources in the organization to achieve results. (Ebitu, Basil et al, 2016). According to Olawale and Garwe (2010), management capacities are sets of knowledge, skills, and competencies that can make the small firm more efficient. Singh et al. (2008) emphasize that management skills are necessary for SMEs to survive and achieve growth. Aylin et al. (2013) state that management skills are a crucial factor for the growth of SMEs and that the lack of management skills is a barrier to growth and is one of the factors that can lead to failure.

- b. Managerial resource barriers:** MSMEs generally lack the understanding and ability to determine the competencies that are required by an employee to fulfil his/her role. These skill gaps exist in all the sectors from micro enterprises to medium scaled businesses (SMEDAN, National Bureau of Statistics 2013).

These identified inadequacies are also supported in a different study by Mathew Philip (2010), where he reviews factors affecting business success of micro and small businesses based internal constraints as management and know-how, products and services, customers and markets, the way of doing business and cooperation finance and Strategy.

2.9 Human Resources Practices in Micro enterprises

Studies have revealed the immense contribution of Micro and Small scale businesses to Nigeria's growing economy. Na-nan, Khahan. (2016) in states that due to their contribution to generating revenue, employment and development for the country, the government has put a premium on SMEs as a driving factor of the country's economy. Businesses, capital, developments and training programs are promoted and encouraged to increase a company's competitiveness in the industry. While the studies by Na-nan, Khahan. (2016), was done for the Thailand economy, its not so much different from what is obtainable in the Nigerian economy. For the same reasons the Nigerian government has set up various institutions that works to ensure growth and survival of MSMEs.

Studies by Osotimehin, K. Jegede et al (2012) additionally supports that Micro and small scale enterprises (MSEs) in Nigeria have not performed creditably well and they have not played expected significant role in economic growth. They equally has not influenced apprentice training so as to accelerate employment and poverty alleviation in order to foster Nigerian economic development. This situation has been of great concern to the government, citizen, operators, practitioners and organized private sectors. With the realization of the potentials of the MSEs, governments at different level in Nigeria have put up a lot of support programmes to promote and sustain their development. It is believed that massive assistance; financial, technical, marketing and managerial from the government are necessary for the SMEs to grow. Some of these institutions include; Small and Medium Enterprises Development of Nigera(SMEDAN), Abuja Enterprise Agency(AEA), Bank of Industry(BOI), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), YouWin Connect Nigeria.

HRM is a strategic management component that is core to the growth of firms both small and large. The peculiarity in the relationship between the success of MEs and the practices of HRM in its daily operations have been studied. According to available empirical information on HRM within MSMEs it is suggested that smaller firms make less use of high performance HRM practices, especially when they operate in an informal and flexible manner than larger organizations. . (Aditi and Ayushi ,2015). It is also found that even when smaller firms practice

any form of Human resource management, the forms are majorly characterized by Informality (Susan, Rowena 2006). Managerial incompetence especially in the field of HRM is the main cause of failure in smaller firms (Dun and Bradstreet (2001).

In microenterprises, both owner-managers and employees are less likely to get formal training. Smaller companies are found to have less formalized performance appraisals, less bonuses based on company productivity and less training than larger firms do. In addition of being characterized as informal, small firms are often held to be less specialized, have to perform a greater variety of tasks than larger firms. (Aditi and Ayushi ,2015).

How much impact does HR practices have on the success of MEs .The significance of Human resources in the development of small firms cannot be overemphasized. According to Lee (2001), human resource capacities form one of the most significant areas for the success of SMEs. This is further emphasized by Chandler and McEvoy (2000), that human resource capacities have a positive effect on the growth of small firms, which increase employee skills and motivation, and eventually result in improving the productivity and long term sustainability of small firms.

2.9.1 The Concept of Performance Management in MSMEs

Every microenterprise is set with different objectives and all operations aim at reaching the objectives. Armstrong (1997) defines Human resource management from the perspective of meeting organizational goals as “a strategic approach to acquiring, developing, managing, motivating and gaining the commitment of the organization’s key resource—the people who work the definitions above fit exactly into an operative function of Human Resource Management, which is Performance Management.

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According to Na-nan, Khahan. (2016) putting in place performance management patterns that are appropriate for SMEs is of great importance and urgency to give these businesses clear directions in setting and following their objectives. This will enable them to continuously develop towards achieving their organizational needs and to sustainably operate under ever-changing environments.

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Human resources is a term with which many organizations describe as the combination of traditionally administrative personnel functions with performance, employee relations and resource planning (Nyameh Jerome,2013)

Human Resource Management HRM& are the policies and practices involved in carrying out the 'people (of human resource aspects of managing position, including recruiting, screening, training, rewarding and appraising (Storey,1992)

A major role of traditional resource management is reconciling the interests of management and the workforce. The traditional approach presumes management and workers having distinct and conflicting goals and needs, with the goal of human resource managers being to effect a reconciliation to drive the organization.

The traditional resource approach takes a resource-centered perspective, directed at ensuring that the organization has adequate and suitable resources for its needs. At the same time, they do not totally identify with management interests and strive to understand and articulate the aspirations and views of the workforce to the management, just as sales representatives understand and articulate the aspirations of the customers to the management.

As outlined above, the process of defining HRM leads us to two different definitions. The first definition of HRM is that it is the process of managing people in organizations in a structured and thorough manner. This covers the fields of staffing (hiring people), retention of people, pay and perks setting and management, performance management, change management and taking care of exits from the company to round off the activities. This is the traditional definition of HRM which leads some experts to define it as a modern version of the Personnel Management function that was used earlier. Human Resource Management in the 21st century has recorded geometric transformation both in its processes, complexity and applicability to enterprises. Mathis, Jackson (2008,2006) clearly provide a transformed definition of HRM as the process of designing management systems to ensure that human talent is used effectively and efficiently to accomplish organizational goals. This definition is a significant shift from older literatures that define HRM as

Human Resource Management was defined by Boxall and Purcell (2003:1) as ‘all those activities associated with the management of employment relationships in the firm. This definition attempts to restrict its meaning to the need to remain competitive has meant that firms in these sectors deploy strategies that make effective use of their resources. This changed business landscape has come about as a result of a paradigm shift in the way businesses and firms view their employees as more than just resources and instead adopt a “people first” approach.

2.10 Performance Management Skills

As earlier mentioned, MSEs are characterized by an owner manager structure, where the owner in most cases directly manages employees in their day to day operations. As already established by previous research , the growth of MSEs is largely dependent on the productivity of employees who are responsible for carrying out work that translates to a Return on Investment. It is there for paramount to state that the manager must possess adequate management skills to manage the performance and to drive the needed output from employees effectively.

Performance management systems are not likely to help employees develop and improve their performance if managers do not have the necessary skills to help employees accomplish these goals. Such skills include being able to serve as coaches, to observe and document performance accurately, to give both positive and negative feedback, and to conduct useful and constructive performance review discussions. Unfortunately, these skills seem to be in short supply.

Herman Aguinis goes on to argue that in a a survey conducted by the consulting firm Watson Wyatt found that, in about 50% of the organizations included in the study, managers are only slightly effective in helping underperforming employees improve their performance, another study including more than 100 organizations in Barbados found that, overall, employees are not satisfied with their performance management system and some of the culprits are “poor management of the process” and “low levels of supervisory motivation.”

Performance Management is a field that goes beyond expecting the employees to perform above board. It is a shared responsibility between a manager supervising effectively to ensure that the employees carry out their roles in the expected performance standards.

Hillman, Schwandt, & Bartz, (1990) agree to the need for managers to build PM competencies in 3 skill areas namely Communication , feedback, and coaching of the employees.

i. Communication Skills

Communication represents an extremely important human element of the employee performance appraisal process because, if information between the manager and staff member cannot be meaningfully exchanged, the appraisal process is likely to falter. The owner-manager needs to

utilize face-to-face communication with staff members throughout the appraisal process Several authors provide the meaning of communication in different contexts,

The word ‘communication’ has been derived from the Latin word ‘communis’ which means ‘common’. Therefore communication refers to making an idea or thought common among two or more people (Singla, 2008-09, p.236) cited by Ankita 2011.

According Keith Davis has defined communication as, “the process of passing and understanding information from one person to another” (Davis, 1967 cited in Singla, 2008-09, p.236). This definition emphasizes on the fact that communication is not just passing the information or thought but also passing an understanding of that information. Other definitions also support that communication requires a sender and a receiver which in terms of this research would be between the Manager and employee. While Louis (1958) gives an on-going perspective of communication, he defines it as a systematic and continuous process of telling, listening and understanding. Peter Little(1977) emphasizes more the expectation of communication, stating that it is a process by which information is transmitted between individuals and / or organizations so that an understanding response results is gotten. This is further agreed by Murphy, Hildebrand et al (1997) as he explain that effective communication is only achieved when it achieves the desired response or reaction from the receiver:

One thing made clear from the above definitions is that Managers must be able to communicate expected performance standards with a clear understanding and feedback from employees. Otherwise it would mean that work will be done with so much pre-suumptions and assumptions.

Ensuring a clear understanding is better explained by *Bartz* (1990,2017) ‘Two-way communication works best in —checking for understanding to ensure that the manager and staff member have a common interpretation of the key elements being discussed’.

Two –way communication also includes factors such as Verbal and nonverbal skills . And these also play an important role in effective communication and establishing common understanding. Examples of nonverbal communication factors are:

-Body movement such as gestures,

- how and where the manager sits (e.g., behind the desk, at a table, side-by-side, or in a chair facing the staff member),
- facial expressions (e.g., smiles or frowns),
- Pitch and tone, the context in which a statement is made, and the use of silence are examples of variables involved in meaningful verbal communication.

Bartz (2017) tries to breakdown what he means by effective communication by providing simple approach to how a manager can apply effective communications daily at work. He identifies other verbal skills that could help improve clarity in managers communicating with employees.

a. Attending: The manager expresses interest in what the staff member is saying and feeling by: Physical attending: general posture, facing the staff member ,maintaining eye contact, sitting in a relaxed rather than a tense position, and having a pleasant facial expression.

Mental attending: paying close attention to the staff member’s verbal and nonverbal behaviors and relating what is being communicated to what has previously been discussed. (This is —in the moment‖ mindfulness.)

b. Reflecting: The manager reflects a sincere desire to understand the staff member’s situation and feelings by reviewing what the staff member has expressed, clarifying it, and periodically summarizing to make sure that the meaning and intent have been correctly understood by both parties.

c. Exploring: The manager continually examines and probes what the staff member is stating to identify specific concerns or problems. If an incomplete explanation or contradictory information is given, the manager asks questions in order to obtain more information and prompt the staff member to provide an —in depth explanation.

d. Self-disclosure: The manager shares thoughts and information with the staff member related to the topic at hand based on the manager’s background experiences. This provides a supportive and constructive relationship concerning what the staff member has communicated.

e. Acceptance: The manager shows appreciation and respect for the staff member as a fellow human being and does not attack the individual’s dignity.

While all the skills may seem so much or complex to apply, it rather calls for flexibility and knowing which skill is needed at every time. The entire goal of communicating with an employee is to be understood and for the message to be implemented. It is this goal that informs the manager on the skills required at any point in time there has to be a communication. The manager should determine when to use each of these five communication skills in order to increase the effectiveness of the communication with a staff member.

ii. Coaching

As at 2010, the National MSME collaboration survey places the number of MSEs in Nigeria to be about 17,261,753 in number fully operating in different parts of the country. Literally this means over 17 million micro businesses are competing for growth and survival to atleast the next strata of business size which is either the Small Business or Medium scale business. This indigenous competition does not immune business owners of micro enterprises from the completion the global market presents. Customers have become more knowledgeable in terms of better services owing to increased access to the internet in even remote areas of Nigeria. The competition has become more aggressive by the day and this certainly has some Human Resource Implications.

Soha & Sleilati, (2016) explain that due to the aggressive competition worldwide, companies are increasingly conscious of the HR prominence. Effective HR is furthermore perceived as a major source of competitive advantage leading companies to success. They further assert that to compete and take the lead, companies are more conscious of their need of a well-trained, qualified and reliable personnel especially that HR capabilities are considered as distinctive and inimitable competitive advantages.

Thus, business owners are increasingly investing in their human capital by attempting to upgrade their capacities and knowledge, and to assist them in acquiring new skills. In support of this assertion that business owners are seeking HR interventions to give them the competitive edge, Travis and Lane (2006) explain that firms need to implement updated techniques to succeed in this rapidly emerging knowledge-based economy and to maintain their position in such a vibrant marketplace.

According to a cited assertion by Soha & Sleilati, (2016) ,Consequently, enterprises are integrating customized interventions, such as coaching sessions that are oriented towards filling employees' personal needs and individual deficiency gaps, with the traditional business practices. These interactive coaching practices work on motivating and inducing employees towards initiative-taking and decision-making. When employees are motivated, they become more productive and enhance organisational performance (Nohria et al., 2008) cited in Soha & Sleilati, (2016) . They conclude that at the end of the coaching interventions, employees feel more confident and more conscious of their heightened capacities and potential.

iii. Coaching As A Performance Management Skill

Describing coaching as a PM skill to be built by business owners, Herman Aguinis (2013) presents Coaching as an ongoing process in which the manager directs, motivates, and rewards employee behavior. He adds that Coaching includes several key functions such as giving advice about what is expected about performance and how to perform well, giving employees' guidance so employees know how to improve their performance, providing employees with support without being controlling, and enhancing employees' confidence and competence

To support Herman's description of coaching PM process of an enterprise, Kilburg (1996, p.142), defines coaching as a 'helping relationship formed between a client who has managerial authority and responsibility in an organization and a consultant who uses a wide variety of behavioral techniques and methods to help the client achieve a mutually identified set of goals to improve his or her professional performance and personal satisfaction'. In context of this research the client is the employee and the consultant is the employer or manager Subsequently, it improves the effectiveness of this employee and enhances his performance.

A more precise definition of coaching that seems to suit the context of this research is given by Bartz(1990) he defines coaching as the assistance given to improve performance when feedback indicates expectations are not met. (Hearn,2016) states that Performance coaching is basically problem-solving applied to a performance issue with a staff member. It should focus on determining what will motivate the staff member to be more productive

The expected outcome of every PM process is that employees are provided the enabling environment to deliver upon set job goals and targets . This explains why business owners should build competencies in skills that will help them achieve that outcome. As long as business operations continue, PM is an on-going activity. And as stated by Herman(2013) The coaching process which is a major skill in PM is also ongoing and cyclical, and it includes the following five components:

- a. Setting developmental goals.
- b. Identifying the resources and strategies needed to achieve the developmental goals (e.g., securing resources that will allow employees to engage in activities to achieve their developmental goals),
- c. Implementing strategies (e.g., enrolling the employee in an online course).
- d. Observing and documenting developmental behaviors (e.g., checking on the progress of the employee toward the attainment of his developmental goals), and
- e. Giving feedback (e.g., providing information to the employee that will help him adjust his current developmental goals and guide his future goals.

Added to the above 5 components of coaching, Bartz(1990) also presents steps for effective coaching which are:

- i. Being direct in stating the purpose of the coaching need, by ultimately identify the task or behavior to be addressed.
- ii. Stating the performance problem or gap, using pre-planned—observable/measurable language. Describe the expected performance, the actual performance and the negative effects of the actual performance.
- iii. Get reaction from the staff member about the feedback just provided by requesting the employee to react.
- iv. Analyze the reasons why performance needs to change.
- v. Explore the possible causes of the performance problem with the staff member.
- vi. Ask the staff member to identify what factors over which he/she has control that may be causing the problem. Jointly explore factors external to the staff member’s behavior that could be impeding performance.

vii. Seek a collaborative solution (if possible).

Coaching is a major step between setting the performance standards and appraising employees based on those standards. The coaching steps if practiced as detailed above contributes to an effective implementation of a standard PM process.

2.11 Formalizing the Performance Management Process

The Human Resources Institute of New Zealand in 2015, gives a perspective of PM from its level of formality. It submits that organizations will have a performance management system in place; however, the difference will be whether the organization has adopted an informal or formal approach towards their employees.

It adds that, it is not uncommon for smaller organizations, due to the nature of their business, not to have specific documented processes in place. Any employee goals and objectives set will be mutually agreed upon between the manager and employee, generally adopting an informal approach. Larger organizations will tend to have a more formal documented process in place for managing employee performance.

Going by the above definitions of PM, it can be implied that small enterprises can stand a chance of surviving their early years, if their employees can produce results that meet the objectives of setting up such enterprises. Yet why is there so much gap in the successes of small firms. A renowned HR expert reveals that ‘many small business owners think of formal employee performance management as "overkill" administrative activities that they can be put off until their business gets bigger. After all, you spend every day working closely with your employees. Why should you implement a formal process that adds administrative burden and stress? (Sean Conard, 2012)

Na-nan, Khahan. (2016) cites various studies (Anderson & Sohal, 1999; Bourne et al., 1999; Hendricks & Singhal, 1997; Hudson, Smart & Bourne, 2001; Jackson & Schuler, 1995; Lado & Wilson, 1994; Milgrom & Roberts, 1995) that have shown that a number of organizations have failed at achieving expected effectiveness from adopting a performance management system.

Some researchers have indicated that organizations whose attempts to apply a performance management system with their operations have failed account for 70 percent (McCunn, 1998). Consequently, those enterprises lost their competitive edge and eventually went out of business.

If owner-managers of MSE are able to understand the advantages of introducing PM processes in their operations, or formalizing their existing processes, which would mean standardizing and documenting or structuring existing PM processes, probably adoption would be easier and resistance would be reduced. Aguinis H. (2013) further details the advantages of implementing a formal PM system in every business;

Motivation to perform is increased: Receiving feedback about one's performance increases the motivation for future performance. Knowledge about how one is doing and recognition about one's past successes provide the fuel for future accomplishments.

Self-esteem is increased: Receiving feedback about one's performance fulfills a basic human need to be recognized and valued at work. This, in turn, is likely to increase employees' self-esteem.

Managers gain insight about subordinates: Direct supervisors and other managers in charge of the appraisal gain new insights into the person being appraised.

Administrative actions are more fair and appropriate: Performance management systems provide valid information about performance that can be used for administrative actions such as merit increases, promotions, and transfers as well as terminations. In general, a performance management system helps ensure that rewards are distributed on a fair and credible basis.

Organizational goals are made clear: The goals of the unit and the organization are made clear, and the employee understands the link between what she does and organizational success.

Employees become more competent: An obvious contribution is that employee performance is improved. In addition, there is a solid foundation for helping employees become more successful by establishing developmental plans.

Employee misconduct is minimized: A good performance management in place provides the appropriate context so that misconduct is clearly defined and labeled as such and identified early on before it leads to sometimes irreversible negative consequences.

Documentation during a PM process is a major implication of referring to a PM system as being formal.

The importance of documenting an employee's progress toward the achievement of developmental goals cannot be overemphasized. Similarly, it is critical to document employee performance in general. Why is this so important? Consider the following reasons:

- a. Minimize cognitive load. Observing and evaluating developmental activities, and performance in general, is a complex cognitive task. Thus, documentation helps prevent memory-related errors.
- b. Create trust. When documentation exists to support evaluations, there is no mystery regarding the outcomes. This, in turn, promotes trust and acceptance of decisions based on the evaluation provided.
- c. Plan for the future. Documenting developmental activities and their outcomes enables discussion about specific facts instead of assumptions and hearsay. A careful examination of these facts permits better planning of developmental activities for the future.

2.12 Criticisms of Performance Management

Notwithstanding the adequate literature that lays bare the merits of PM in business process, dissatisfaction with performance management (PM) has had a long history. Managers and employees alike have frustrations with the system, and numerous calls for the elimination of performance appraisal have been made over the years (e.g., Scholtes, 1999). The dissatisfaction and calls for elimination have created pressure for change in the practice of PM. L. Cardy, Robert. (2015).

Companies need to look closely at their performance management and appraisal systems, because of their inherent potential to harm productivity and the relationships between employees and managers (Newton & Finlay 1996)).

Performance management systems need to be continuously re-aligned and re-invigorated (Ibec (2007). Failure to continuously re-align and re-invigorate the performance management system may present difficulties such as lack of commitment from both senior and line managers, this in turn may lead to decisions around ratings and reward been non transparent (Marcus 2008).

In their view, Mankins & Steele (2005) claim that companies rarely track performance against long term plans. The effect being a disconnect between results and forecasts in future investment decisions.

According to Weightman (2001), performance measurement unavoidably involves judging people in some way. Judging people sometimes can produce a negative result on interpersonal relationship and productivity as well. Marcus (2008), in commenting on the opinion of Bacal (1998) “states that performance management assumes that if you focus on results, then you are much more likely to succeed. This makes sense - you set goals, reach goals, and you get what is desired. The problem is that a sole focus on results neglects organizational and system issues that need to be in place for the results to happen. He goes on to state that organizations set up barriers for the people to do their work. This happens because o f a focus on short term, immediate results”. Again Bacal (1998) argue that performance management systems cause problems for organizations. He states that traditional performance management systems can foster a lack of collective responsibility for the achievement of organizational goals, encourage competition rather than cooperation, and impede the development of effective teamwork (Marcus, 2008). Marcus also state that performance management system is designed to enhance the responsibility of individuals. But at the same time, by focusing on this responsibility reduces an employee’s responsibility to the organization and to activities that are not “his or her job”.

Alfred & Potter (1995), argue that performance appraisals, as part of the performance management system, can be be time-wasting and having no value as the information received during the appraisals is just filed afterwards and not utilized fully. Hunt (1992) argues that t appraisal systems are often poorly designed, overambitious, inadequately resourced.

According to Brown & Armstrong (1999), there is a need for Performance management systems to be developed along ethical lines. They propose an ethical framework that should be considered in the designing of a performance management system, including “(1) respect for the individual, (2) mutual respect, (3) transparency of decision-making and (4) procedural fairness” Marcus (2008) reports that “the ethical component is very important, particularly given the reliance on the judgement of the appraiser, and the relationship between the appraisee and appraiser. It is an issue that the appraiser comes with their own set of biases, and judgement systems, which affects the outcome of the appraisal”. According to Price (2000), higher than average ratings can be attributed to factors such as preserving morale, avoiding confrontation, and the perceived image of the management of an underrated department.

Marcus (2008) states that “because performance management systems are implemented for many reasons they are often overburdened with expectations. If the reason for the performance management system is to reward individuals, then staff will expect their pay to be linked to their performance. Senior staff might be told that the performance management system will enable them to identify and make provision for achievers and underperformers. They will expect that the system is able to assist them in making these identifications. Directors might feel that the performance management system will improve organizational effectiveness, and will then expect it to do so”

Although these criticism hold some water and lessons business owners can draw from and improve in their own structures, the benefits of having a defined Performance Management structure outweighs some of its criticisms.

This research will focus on finding out if any of the above components of Performance Management exists in the selected sample used in this study. Personnel practices are beginning to emerge as important for small firms, previously even business Management textbooks did not devote enough coverage to the relevant personnel management concerns for small businesses, as compared to topics on finance, marketing and planning. Personnel management issues but literatures are beginning to focus on the impact of PM practices on small firms. It is hoped that findings from this research would contribute to the Literature coverage in this much information gapped concern for small businesses.

The study attempts to answer the following questions,

- a. Are there existing use of Performance Management components in the operations Micro enterprises?
- b. Which components are mostly used and which ones are mostly lacking.
- c. How structured and formal are the PM processes adopted by small business.
- d. How can existing PM structures be modified to harness its optimal value to the survival of Micro enterprise beyond its first 3 years.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Morgan, Gliner and Harmon (1999) state that if there is none or little information available about the subject, the researcher must perform an exploratory research so that the grasp of the phenomena or interest on the subject matter could be obtained. The Literature review provides evidence that very little is known about Micro enterprises as a sector of small Scale businesses more so as it concerns Performance management.

This research serves two purposes; exploring as well as explaining a phenomenon. This research will be both explorative and descriptive to get findings into the research topic. This will inform the research conclusions and recommendations.

The study also employs a qualitative research methodology, this is in agreement with (Creswell, 2002) who states that qualitative approach would be suited when one was trying to understand a concept or phenomena where little research has been done.

3.2 Research Question and Objectives

In today's business world, competition drives the market and determines the survival of any enterprise. This market-driven competition cuts across Micro, Small and Medium Scale enterprises and does not show mercy to the size of a workforce. Performance Management is key to the survival of any business because it ensure that employees are contributing correctly to set goals and objectives of that business . This research aims to respond the the following major questions;

1. Do Micro-enterprises adopt any component of Performance Management in their daily operations?

2. If there is an existing structure for Performance Management, How formal is the structure?
3. What is the impact of not having a PM structure to the survival of the business?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the existence and components of Performance Management in selected MSEs.
2. To study the impact of the absence or existence of Performance Management components on selected MSEs.
3. To provide some meaningful suggestion to MSEs towards improving or modifying existing use of Performance Management components.

3.3 Data Collection

The study used questionnaires administered in depth Interview to obtain its primary data. The study is done using unstructured in-depth interviews as a technique to get data. This is because the study's aim was to explore the existence of the Performance Management in Micro enterprises, It also allows the interviewer to discover the respondent's ideas, views, suggestions and queries and further allows the respondent more freedom in responding his or her own word' (Plooy, 2002).

The approach is time consuming and requires the researcher record all that had been said. The researcher believed that the interview had the advantage of providing additional information which could not otherwise have been obtained if other techniques were to be used for this study.

This is also based on Saunders et al. (2009) which states that with exploratory research the researcher should be prepared to change direction if new information and insights appears.

3.4 Questionnaire Design

According to some empirical studies, the design of a questionnaires must be evaluated with the aim of achieving relevancy, accuracy and questionnaire design Presser and Blair (1994), Singh (2000), Tanur (1992).

The questionnaires of this research consist of three major sections A, B C and D; the first section A contains 11 questions of which the first 3 questions served as baseline data investigating the length of business existence, number of employees, literacy level of employees. The other part of section A covers the existence of a communicated mission and overall business objective, clearly stated job description from business owner to the employees.

The section B contains 8 questions that speak to the performance evaluation processes used, the existence of mutually set goals and timeframe and regularity of performance evaluation processes. The section C, checks for the use of outcomes on performance evaluations conducted, the recognition of the impact of Performance management on employee contribution to the business and the level of formality of the existing Performance management structures in selected businesses.

3.5 Sample Size and Selection Criteria

A sample has also to be representative of a population. The sample is used in order to retrieve new information that is relevant to a large group of people identified as a population.

Delahave and Sekaran (2001) mentioned that the use of judgment sampling permits information to be secured from specific target groups and the required information for the research. Furthermore, quota sampling ensures that representativeness of a certain group is adequate in the research (Davis 2005).

The respondents used as sample in this study are owners and managers of selected enterprises. 10 owners and managers of small businesses were interviewed ineptly to respond to the research questions detailed above. Questionnaires were also distributed to over XXX respondents.

Performance Management is a process that is implemented via a top down approach. The first process of Performance Management starts with setting business goals and objectives which is then cascaded down to functional units of the enterprise. The initial direction and the initial goals set for the continuous improvement teams flow down from, and are determined by, top management the mission and business objective of the enterprise comes from its owner and is then cascaded down to supervisors or managers if they exist down to employees who would be responsible for meeting the objectives.

More so as one of the objectives of this research is to provide recommendations to modifying existing PM structures, it would be more effective to get a business owner to adopt a recommendation and enforce its implementation. This explains the reason why the owners and managers of the selected enterprises were chosen as respondents for this research.

The Enterprises selected are Micro in nature, which is explained in the Literature as a business that has 1 to 10m employees in its workforce. Survey for all selected businesses was done by their owners or managers. Each business owner respondent is required to provide information of the number of employees that work for them.

To ensure a fair sample selection. The researcher will adopt the assertion Lapan & Quartaroli (2009) which states that random selection involves a small group of people being selected at random so that each participant has an identical opportunity of being chosen from the large group of people, this method of selection therefore provides fair representation.

All respondents were business owners operating in Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory of Abuja.

Below outlines the enterprises under this study:

	Enterprise operational area	Number of respondents
1	Management consulting	5
2	Photography and video services	2
3	Legal services	1
4	Bakery	3
5	Events Management services	2

6	IT consultancy	2
7	Printing services	2
8	Beauty care services	1
9	Daycare services	1
10	Herbal tea extract services	2
11	Fashion design and Tailoring services	1
12	Micro thrift financial services	1

3.6 Data Reliability

Reliability and validity of the study According to Neuman (2011) reliability refers to the dependability or consistency of the data. The researcher used reliable sources to ensure dependability and consistency to collect data. Questionnaires were issued only to business owners and managers who were saddled with the responsibility of managing the performance of their employees. The same question as attached in appendix B was used throughout the data collection exercise to ensure consistency.

Questionnaires were issued in both hard and soft copy formats, in-person and via emails. In a few cases some respondents could not access their questionnaires via any of the aforementioned sources hence the researcher had to administer the questionnaires via phone calls ensuring that survey questions are strictly followed.

3.7 Limitations

After issuing the questionnaire to the first set of respondents, they complained that they could not understand certain technical terms, such as Performance Management systems and performance appraisals, key performance indicators etc. So the questionnaire had to be retrieved and redesigned with simpler and everyday terms that portray the same meanings as the technical words not fully understood.

When analyzing data from questionnaires, the researcher that some respondents did not respond to some questions. This was also captured in the data presentation as blank response.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations observed by the researcher in the course of this project include;

- a. Proper referencing of Literatures and existing contributions in this field of study.
- b. Seeking verbal consent from the respondents before distributing questionnaires. Respondents were also informed that their willingness to respond was voluntary.
- c. All questionnaires clearly indicated that every information given would be used for academic purposes only.
- d. To ensure confidentiality of the survey, the survey tool did not include any section for naming the respondents.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION

4.1 DATA PRESENTATION

The research findings is being presented in chart format to show responses drawn from survey. Twenty three (23) enterprises were studied by Primary sourced data. Business owners of these enterprise responded to a 24 question survey to draw insight to the Performance Management processes operationalized in their individual respective businesses. The data is presented as follows;

Q1. How long has your business been in exist

Q2. How many employees do you have in your business

This question was asked as an insight to check that literacy was not a contributory factor to the level of formality of performance Management processes.

Q3 How many of your employees can read and write?

Q4 Do you have an overall business mission or objective or goal that has been communicated to all staff?

Q5. Have all employees' personal goals been discussed to check for any alignment with overall business goals?

Q6. As an owner/manager/supervisor, do you at any time involve employees in setting the expectations on their tasks

Q7. Are employees given job descriptions/roles when they resume?

Q8. How do employees mostly receive their job descriptions/roles when they start work?

Q9. Are Job descriptions/roles for all functions clear and followed?

Q10. Do you evaluate employees' performance based on their entire previously set job description/roles?

Q11. Do you always get a clear feedback from employees on their understanding of their roles?

Q12. Do you set out a particular period when you let employees know how they are performing?

Q13. Is the period of performance evaluation done regularly?

Q14. Are expected outcomes for each job role mutually decided between employer and subordinates?

Q15. Do you set specific performance targets to be achieved in a certain timeframe?

Q16. Do employees get to ever evaluate their own performance by themselves?

Q17. Do employees know that their performance will be evaluated based on the expected outcomes?

Number of response

Q18 Are your employees evaluated based on expected job roles previously agreed on?

Number of response

Q19 Does the Performance evaluation in your business involve any form of grading or ratings?

Number of response

Q20 Have the performance of any employee improve due to the current way you evaluate

Number of response

Q21. Are rewards/ promotions/ trainings/ bonus/recognition strictly based on the performance evaluation?

Number of response

Q22. Does every Performance measure have a clear definition?

Number of response

Q23. Can you attribute any changes in employee performance to an evaluation conducted?

Number of response

Q24. Formality is defined by paper documentation. How would you consider your performance Management process?

Number of response

4.2 Interpretation of Data

The objective of his research is aimed at assessing the existence of these components in the operational processes of Micro enterprises. This formed the basis of the questions in the survey. To ensure ease of comprehension of the questions and avoid use of HR technical terms, the researcher simplified all survey question, using descriptive terms that explain each of the components. The components of Performance Management system according to (Prachi Juneja, 2018) is listed as;

- a. Communicate overall Business Goal to all employees.
- b. Performance Development and Planning
- c. Performance Monitoring
- d. Performance Appraisal and Reviewing:
- e. Feedback on the Performance
- f. Rewarding good performance
- g. Performance Improvement Plans

The breakdown of the survey questions as it relates to the components of performance management is as follows.

	Survey question	Component of performance management
1	Do you have an overall business mission or objective or goal that has been communicated to all staff	A. Develop clear Job Descriptions that meet business objectives
2	Are employees given job descriptions/roles when they resume	
3	Are Job descriptions/roles for all positions clear and followed	
4	How do employees mostly receive their job descriptions/roles when they start work?	

5	As an owner/manager/supervisor, do you at any time involve employees in setting the expectations on their tasks	B. Performance Planning Performance Monitoring
6	Have employees personal goals been ever discussed to check for any alignment with overall business goals	
7	Do you always get a clear feedback from employees on their understanding of their roles	
	Does every Performance measure have a clear definition?	
8	Are expected outcomes for each job role mutually decided between subordinates/employer and superiors	
9	Do you evaluate employees' performance based on their entire job description/roles?	C. Performance Appraisal and Reviewing Feedback on the Performance
10	Do you set out a particular period when you let employees know how they are performing	
11	Is the period of performance evaluation done regularly	
12	Do you set specific performance targets to be achieved in a certain timeframe	
14	Do employees get to ever evaluate their own performance by them selves	
15	Do employees know that their performance will be evaluated based on the expected outcomes	
16	Are your employees evaluated based on expected job roles previously agreed on	
17	Does the Performance evaluation in your business involve any form of grading or ratings	
18	Have the performance of any employee improve due to the current way you evaluate their performance.	D. Rewarding good performance

19	Are rewards/ promotions/ trainings/ bonus/recognition strictly based on the performance evaluation?	E. Performance Improvement Plans
20	Formality is defined by paper documentation. How would you consider your performance Management process	
21	Can you attribute any changes in employee performance to an evaluation conducted	

Of the total number of businesses studied, data reveals the percentage existence of each component as follows:

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 CONCLUSION

The study's aim was to evaluate the existence Performance Management components in Micro scale enterprises with a view to understand its contribution to the survival of MSEs beyond its first 3 years.

Data available from the study reveal that all 23 businesses individually adopt some of the components of PM. These components are adopted in varying levels as shown in the diagram of levels of PM . None of the 23 businesses practiced all the components. The first two PM components mostly practiced by the 23 selected businesses are Performance planning, monitoring and appraisals. The components least practiced by these businesses are rewarding good performance and Performance Improvement Plan.

One of the indicators also studied in this research is the formality of the process of PM by the sample. And the study shows that 14 out of the 23 enterprises defined the PM processes as informal. This is about 62% of the entire businesses studied.

As earlier stated in the Literature Review section, not much studies have been done in the area of Micro enterprises and the factors that contribute to their growth and survival. Hopefully this study contributes to the gap and provides an insight recommendations on PM structures in view of its relationship with Mses.

A detailed study by Herman Aguinis (2013) in his text book devoted to Performance management shows that, organizations with formal and systematic performance management systems are 51% more likely to perform better than the other organizations in terms of financial outcomes, and 41% more likely to perform better than the other organizations in terms of other outcomes such as customer satisfaction, employee retention, and other important metrics. He

adds that it is not surprising that senior executives of companies listed in the Sunday Times list of best employers in the United Kingdom believe that performance management is one of the top two most important HR management priorities in their organizations.

Based on the above literature and other available studies from known experts PM is key to the survival and growth of every business.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Businesses exist to grow and make profit while doing so and several factors can inhibit both growth and profitability. Studies have earlier shown that one of the major challenges of Micro and Small Enterprises is poor managerial structures. Performance Management as a function of Human Resource Management is the only function that deals majorly with the effective implementation of business goals and objectives. This means that no matter how great and logical a Business goal or mission sounds, its implementation and conversion to output defines its worth. Performance Management plays that key role between Great business Goals and achieving them. This invariable means that business owners need to increase focus on adopting formal PM structures.

From this study it is also recommended that businesses should formalize their existing PM structures to improve the outcome of employee's performance. The merits of formalizing PM structures has been given by (Jenna Puckett, 2015 and R. Khera 2018)

- a. Provides increased focus on driving business results.
- b. Produces an empowered and engaged workforce.
- c. PM structure will not only boost employee morale and confidence, but also help managers avoid any communication gaps in the process.
- d. It increase accountability from employees, goals and keep performance Indicators are mutually set by both owners or supervisors and employees themselves.
- e. Additionally, it will also help in providing employees with a clear picture of what is expected from them and what they need to accomplish their tasks.

- f. Adopting PM processes also help employers, who mostly owner-managers understand where to focus their efforts and how to prioritize their work to bring the best ROI. Instead of micromanaging employees.

5.3 NEED FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

In 2001, the foremost regulatory body for small enterprises in Nigeria, SMEDAN in its National policy for MSMEs published that notwithstanding the numerous challenges faced by the informal business sector of Nigeria, Micro enterprises are numerous hence even a small improvement in their productivity and output will mean result in large improvements in employment, income and productivity. This lends more weight to the value of Micro enterprises to Nigeria's economy.

For such a sector that is also estimated to account for over 25% of total employment and 20% of GDP in Nigeria (SMEDAN, 2007). The number of research by both institutions and economic experts is quite few. Nigeria's informal economy still remains an enigma as it has neither been comprehensively studied nor understood. Oduh et al (2008).

There is a dire need for more research of the informal sector where Micro enterprises belong to. This will enable National driven solutions to the challenges facing this almost neglected but valuable contributor to Nigeria's economy.

Additionally, although this study shows that more than 50% of the sample have existed beyond its first 5years, more study could be carried out to investigate the quality of the number of years in existence in terms of expansion, productivity and profitability index.

CHAPTER 6

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Appendix 1

Questionnaire used to collect data for study

***Disclaimer:** The data gathered through this survey would be used exclusively for the purpose of academic research only.*

***Project focus:** Evaluation of Performance Management components in Micro Scale Enterprise: Its contribution to their survival beyond the first 3 years of existence. Accepting fill makes you a voluntary respondent.*

SECTION A

1. How long has your business been in existence?
 - a. 0-3 Years -
 - b. 3-5 Years-
 - c. 5 -10 Years-
 - d. More than 15 Years-

- 2) How many employees do you have in your business
 - a. 1-5:
 - b. 5-10

- 3) How many of your employees can read and write
 - a. 1-5 of employees:
 - b. 5-10 of employees

- 4) Do you have an overall business mission or objective or goal that has been communicated to all staff.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

- 5) Have employees personal goals been ever discussed to check for any alignment with overall business goals.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Other: _____

- 6) As an owner/manager/supervisor, do you at any time involve employees in setting the expectations on their tasks.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

7. Are employees given job descriptions/roles when they resume.

- a. Yes
 - b. No
8. How do employees mostly receive their job descriptions/roles when they start work.
- a. By mutual discussion between owner/ manager and employee.
 - b. By a formal document, detailing their expected Job roles.
9. Are Job descriptions/roles for all positions clear and followed.
- a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Not always.
10. Do you evaluate employees performance based on their entire job description/roles.
- a. Yes
 - b. No, I identify some key roles and evaluate my employees' performance based on those roles.
11. Do you always get a clear feedback from employees on their understanding of their roles.
- a. Yes
 - b. No

SECTION B

12. Do you set out a particular period when you let employees know how they are performing?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Other:_____
13. IS the period of performance evaluation done regularly;
- a. Yes
 - b. No
14. Are expected outcomes for each job role mutually decided between subordinates/employer and superiors?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
15. Do you set specific performance targets to be achieved in a certain timeframe?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
16. Do employees get to ever evaluate their own performance by themselves;
- a. Yes

- b. No
- 17. Do employees know that their performance will be evaluated based on the expected outcomes.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
- 18. Are your employees evaluated based on expected job roles previously agreed on.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
- 19. Does the Performance evaluation in your business involve any form of grading or ratings?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

SECTION C

- 20. Have the performance of any employee improve due to the current way you evaluate their performance.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
- 21. Are rewards/ promotions/ trainings/ bonus/recognition strictly based on the performance evaluation?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
- 22. Does every Performance measure have a clear definition?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
- 23. Can you attribute any changes in employee performance to an evaluation conducted?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
- 24. Formality is defined by paper documentation. How would you consider your performance Management process
 - a. Formal
 - b. Informal